

Extraction Studies of Metal Xanthates : Extraction of Cu, Co, Ni and Bi with Pyridine/Ethyl Acetate (1:4) and Photometric Determination of Cu, Co and Bi

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Manuscript received 12 September 1973; accepted 15 February 1974

A new solvent system has been developed for the extraction of metal xanthates. Different parameters involved in the extraction study have been studied in detail and conditions are given for maximum extraction of the metal ions. The interference of other ions has been studied. The extracts can be directly used for their estimation by photometric methods.

PYRIDINE/ETHYL acetate has been described as a new solvent in the extraction of metal xanthates. The present paper relates to the study of other parameters involved in the extraction technique. The earlier results revealed that the extraction of nickel in ethyl acetate in the presence of pyridine is more efficient². The extracts can be directly used for the photometric determination of these ions.

Reagents and Apparatus

Potassium ethyl xanthate was prepared from distilled alcohol and CS₂ and was purified by Dewitt and Roper³ technique. All other reagents used were of analytical grade. Demineralised water was used throughout the work.

ERMA Photoelectric colorimeter Model AE-II of ERMA Optical Works, Tokyo, Japan has been used.

Extraction Technique

When 1 ml. of 4% xanthate is added to different aliquots of metal ions, the latter gets precipitated. This becomes clear on the addition of 1 ml. of pyridine. To this 1 ml. of 5M sodium formate is added and the aqueous volume is made to 5 ml. with demineralised water in a separating funnel to which 4 ml. of ethyl acetate are added. The mixture is thoroughly equilibrated for 2 mins. After settling both the layers are separated. The organic extract is washed with 1 ml. of sodium formate and the color absorbance is measured using a blue filter 420 nm. The addition of formate as a salting out agent enhances the % extraction and reduces the solubility and both the layers are of equal volumes. For an almost complete extraction of the metal ions a two-stage batch extraction is required.

The applicability of Nernst's distribution law is verified by adding different aliquots of metal ions and finding out the amount of metal ions extracted into the organic layer. The results revealed that the distribution law is valid in its simple form 0.05-2.0 mg. The values of D obtained by volumetric methods are Cu-10.76, Co-32.33, Ni-1.66, Bi-10.76. Beer's law is valid over the following ranges: Cu-0.04 mg/ml., Co-0.01-0.055 mg/ml, Bi-0.06-0.14 mg/ml.

Copper (II): The absorption maximum is at 435 nm. The measurements at 420 nm are quite accurate, 0.1% EDTA in aqueous layer masks Co and Ni. The results are given in Table 1.

Cobalt: Measurements made at 420 nm are quite accurate, 3% thiourea masks copper. Quantities of nickel upto 0.1 mg in 0.2 mg of cobalt do not interfere with the determination of cobalt in the presence of nickel (Table 1).

TABLE 1- PHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CU, CO AND BI XANTHATE EXTRACTS AFTER 2 EXTRACTIONS WITH PYRIDINE/ETHYL ACETATE. ABSORBANCE MEASURED AT 420 NM.

Sl.No.	Metal ion	Amount taken mg	Amount extracted mg	% Extracted
1.	Copper	0.100	0.099	99.0
		0.150	0.149	99.33
		0.200	0.1985	99.12
		0.250	0.2482	99.28
		0.300	0.2975	99.16
2.	Cobalt	0.200	0.199	99.9
		0.300	0.2987	99.57
		0.400	0.3996	99.65
		0.500	0.498	99.6
3.	Bismuth	0.800	0.790	98.8
		1.000	0.992	99.2
		1.200	1.185	98.75
		1.400	1.180	98.58

Bismuth (III): Absorbance is maximum at 366–370 nm. Measurements upto 420 nm although less sensitive are fairly accurate. This extraction in presence of 0.1% NaCN and 0.1% EDTA in aqueous layer is selective for bismuth in the presence of Cu, Co, Ni etc. Tl(III) interferes.

Nickel (II): The extraction of nickel xanthate into ethyl acetate is very efficient in the presence of pyridine, when the yellow colour of nickel xanthate changes to light green. The absorbancy is maximum at 420 nm but the sensitivity is not good.² After extraction pyridine is stripped with hydrochloric acid to restore the yellow color and the absorbancy can be measured.

Interferences

Molybdate, tungstate, chromate, sulphate, nitrate, chloride, acetate, fluoride, tartrate, thiosulphate, iodide, iron, chromium, thorium, aluminium and zirconium do not interfere with the extraction of these metal ions. Thallium, high concentration of ammonia and citrate interferes with this extraction.

Discussion

Supplee and Bellis⁴ colorimetric procedure for copper as xanthate requires rigid control of conditions and the extract on standing becomes turbid probably due to the precipitation of copper xanthate or sulphur. With increasing concentration of ammonia the color rapidly fades. By the use of pyridine in the

extraction technique the procedure has been made quite simple and sensitive and the extract can be used directly for trace analysis.

Pyridine considerably improves the range of extraction of bismuth xanthate in ethyl acetate. Yellow color of nickel xanthate is considerably more sensitive as compared to the greenish color of cobalt xanthate. The yellow color of nickel xanthate changes to greenish on the addition of pyridine due to the formation of nickel xanthate pyridine adduct². The sensitivity of direct measurement of this color is very poor as the extract has a zero absorbancy even when 0.04 mg/ml nickel is present in the extract. The sensitivity has been improved by measuring the yellow color after stripping the pyridine with HCl.

References

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